

TEAL2HEAL WALK OF FEATS FUNDRAISER

SITUATIONAL ANALYSIS

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TEAL 2 HEAL WALK OF FEATS PR CAMPAIGN

Whitewater PR Company is rolling out a public relations campaign for Teal 2 Heal, highlighting the Walk of Feats fundraiser to support ovarian cancer patients in central Wisconsin and to bring awareness to ovarian cancer. The event, usually hosted on a Saturday in September, offers an "amazing race-style" walk. The fundraiser brings in various people, including families, millennials, retirees, and everyone in between. With a mix of fun challenges and a point system designed for inclusivity, the fundraiser culminates in prizes for participants. Comfort bags, funded by the proceeds, are then crafted for patients with ovarian cancer and their affected families. The rest of the proceeds go to research on ovarian cancer. This public relations campaign will enhance Teal 2 Heal's visibility, particularly by using the Walk of Feats fundraiser. In turn, Teal 2 Heal's visibility will help raise awareness about ovarian cancer and the importance of early detection. The nonprofit organization Teal 2 Heal is explained in detail below.

TEAL 2 HEAL NONPROFIT ORGANIZATION OVERVIEW

Teal 2 Heal, established in central Wisconsin, is a non-profit organization created to support individuals and families affected by ovarian cancer. This condition often lacks sufficient support networks (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). The founders, Michele and Leigh Olszewski, recognized the need for increased awareness and support for those battling this disease and decided to start a nonprofit organization to address this issue.

The nonprofit organization seeks to enhance awareness of ovarian cancer and provide direct support to those affected. This support includes distributing care packages to patients and making financial contributions to entities engaged in cancer research and developing support

groups. Efforts like these are essential due to the difficulties in reaching ovarian cancer patients directly because of privacy laws and practical hurdles (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). Teal 2 Heal depends on the support of healthcare workers, especially nurses, to bridge the gap with patients. Teal 2 Heal's geographic focus on central Wisconsin works well with the efforts of the Wisconsin Ovarian Cancer Alliance, which covers the south and southeastern regions of the state. By concentrating resources in specific areas like Mosinee, Wausau, and Steven's Point, Teal 2 Heal ensures that this area of Wisconsin is also covered (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024).

Ovarian cancer, despite its severity, does not receive the same level of public attention as other cancers. Its symptoms are often deceptive, mimicking less severe conditions and leading to late diagnoses with significantly worse prognoses (*What Should I Know About Screening?*, 2023). Teal 2 Heal is committed to educating the public about the importance of recognizing early signs of ovarian cancer and the critical need for support for those diagnosed with it (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024).

A dedicated team, including Leigh, the founding Director, and Michele, the President and spokesperson, drive the organization. They are supported by Sarah, who manages social media efforts to broaden outreach, and Kaylee, responsible for procuring supplies and securing sponsorships. Below, the mission statement of Teal 2 Heal is described.

ORGANIZATION MISSION STATEMENT

The mission of Teal 2 Heal nonprofit organization is to raise awareness of ovarian cancer and how severe its effects can be on patients, survivors, families, and friends involved. Overall, the organization's mission is to raise awareness about the disease.

WALK OF FEATS FUNDRAISER EVENT OVERVIEW

Teal 2 Heal organizes an annual fundraiser to support ovarian cancer patients and their families. The event, held on a Saturday in September, involves a race-style competition designed to be inclusive of various demographics, including families with children in strollers, millennials, retired individuals, and everyone in between (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). The fundraiser attracts many participants and volunteers, with one or two volunteers stationed at every game along the walk route.

The walk begins early in the morning, with participants starting to show up between 7 a.m. and 9 a.m. For those who didn't pre-register, registration opens at 8 a.m. The registration fee is \$25 for an individual and \$50 for a team of two. Payments are accepted through PayPal. The event does not offer welcome bags or aspirin but light refreshments like water and bananas. The only source of income for the event is through the registration fees (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024).

The walk route stretches from one park of Mosinee, follows a river trail, and ends in another park. Along the way, participants engage in various minute-to-win-it games, such as ping pong and bean bag tosses, accumulating points. The points system is adjusted to ensure fairness, allowing full family participation (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). At the end of the race, the team with the most points wins prizes donated by local businesses. Prizes vary yearly and include items such as Moscow Mule baskets, electric weed whackers, pots and pans sets, hair care baskets, gift certificates, and landscape artwork.

Proceeds from the event registration fees are used to create comfort bags for ovarian cancer patients in collaboration with local businesses. These bags may include items like heat

pads, massages, water bottles, and food gift cards, aiming to alleviate some of the stress faced by the patients (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024).

Additionally, the organization is exploring opportunities to support ovarian cancer research and makes donations to Aspirus Wausau Hospital, known for its significant ovarian cancer wing.

Teal 2 Heal SWOT Analysis

A SWOT analysis explains the organization's strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and strengths. Below is a SWOT analysis of Teal 2 Heal nonprofit organization.

Strengths

Strategic healthcare partnerships enhance patient outreach, which Teal 2 Heal has been developing and can be even more so with additional hospitals, as explained below. A dedicated leadership team, including Leigh as Founding Director, Michele as Founding Director and President, Sarah as social media manager, and Kaylee in procurement and sponsorships, drives the mission forward. Collaborations with groups like the Wisconsin Ovarian Cancer Alliance expand reach without duplicating efforts in areas.

Weaknesses

The organization faces privacy and logistical hurdles in reaching patients directly, hindered by stringent privacy laws (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). Public awareness of ovarian cancer is relatively low compared to other cancers, which can impact fundraising and advocacy efforts (*Ovarian Cancer Risk Factors / Risk Factors for Ovarian Cancer*, 2024). As a non-profit, inherent resource constraints could limit the scope of operations, including funding, staffing, and available resources. There's also a reliance on a small leadership team, which poses a risk if key individuals cannot fulfill their roles, potentially disrupting the organization's continuity and effectiveness.

Opportunities

The organization has the opportunity to reach out to hospitals for support other than Aspirus Wausau Hospital. Initiating awareness campaigns like this one can educate the public about ovarian cancer, potentially leading to earlier detection and improved patient outcomes. Along with the existing partnerships and support from local businesses, there is also scope for collaborative ventures with other medical institutions, other cancer support groups, and other businesses that could provide sponsorship and support. Additionally, as described below, within the second key public, there is substantial potential in utilizing social media platforms to expand reach and connect with a broader and younger audience.

Threats

The organization must navigate potential threats, including changes in healthcare privacy regulations that could further complicate direct patient contact. There's also the possibility of competing organizations searching for the same resources and public attention, which could dilute the overall impact and support of ovarian cancer awareness. Economic downturns pose a significant risk, as they can lead to a decrease in financial contributions, adversely affecting the organization's funding. Additionally, unforeseen events such as pandemics, like COVID-19, or other crises could disrupt normal operations and the organization's ability to conduct fundraising events or distribute care packages.

PROBLEM

Teal 2 Heal confronts several challenges in its mission to spread awareness about ovarian cancer and support individuals and families affected by the disease. Key among these is the difficulty in raising awareness due to low public visibility. Also, there are difficulties with early diagnosis due to that specific cancer's deceptive symptoms and no current testing for it (*What*

Should I Know About Screening?, 2023). The organization also grapples with reaching patients directly, hindered by privacy laws and logistical issues, making partnerships with healthcare professionals and institutions crucial yet complex to navigate (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). Moreover, Teal 2 Heal faces the common non-profit hurdles of resource constraints and the need for effective public education and engagement strategies. Although awareness is a goal, this public relations campaign focuses on behavioral change, which includes getting people to attend the Walk of Feats fundraising event. More attendance will, in turn, create awareness. Below, Teal 2 Heal's geographical and demographical publics are explained in detail, along with the use of data points for faster information gathering.

TEAL 2 HEAL'S GEOGRAPHICAL AND DEMOGRAPHICAL PUBLICS

Wausau Wisconsin

Based on the U.S. Census Bureau data, the Wausau, Wisconsin, community has a population of 39,906 people (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The gender distribution across various age groups is relatively balanced, with a slight predominance of females in the older age brackets, for example, 65 years and over (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The household composition in Wausau indicates a variety of living situations, with more females than males living alone and a total of 17,300 households with an average size of 2.24 individuals (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). Family households average slightly larger, with a size of 2.95 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

In terms of demographics, the majority of Wausau's population is white, with 31,298 residents (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020), and smaller representations of other races, including 4,757 Asian residents and 672 Black or African American residents (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020). The

area's economic status is diverse, with income levels spanning from less than \$10,000 to over \$200,000, suggesting a mix of economic conditions with a median income of \$59,259 and a mean income of \$78,497 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

The educational levels show that 91.4% of the population has at least graduated from high school, and 31% hold a bachelor's degree or higher (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). This educational attainment is reflected in the occupational distribution, with many residents employed in management, business, science, and arts occupations, as well as service and sales jobs (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). Notably, there is a high gender disparity in natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations, with 99.1% male representation, and a notable difference in production, transportation, and material moving occupations as well (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). Below are the demographical and geographical data points on the public of Wausau, Wisconsin, for easier viewing.

Wausau Population Totals and Gender (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 15 to 19 years old total 6.2% | 6.1% male | 6.4% female (2494 total)
- 20 to 24 years old total 6.2% | 6.9% male | 5.6% female (2483 total)
- 25 to 29 years old total 7.3% | 7.8% male | 6.9% female (2922 total)
- 30 to 34 years old total 6.8% | 8.4% male | 5.4% female (2733 total)
- 35 to 39 years old total 7.0% | 6.7% male | 7.4% female (2809 total)
- 40 to 44 years old total 6.8% | 6.8% male | 6.7% female (2695 total)
- 45 to 49 years old total 4.9% | 5.0% male | 4.8% female (1942 total)
- 50 to 54 years old total 5.6% | 6.2% male | 5.0% female (2225 total)
- 55 to 59 years old total 5.5% | 5.6% male | 5.4% female (2189 total)
- 60 to 64 years old total 7.0% | 6.8% male | 7.3% female (2813 total)

- 65 to 69 years old total 6.8% | 7.2% male | 6.3% female (2703 total)
- 70 to 74 years old total 3.7% | 3.5% male | 4.0% female (1491 total)
- 75 to 79 years old total 2.5% | 2.2% male | 2.7% female (986 total)
- 80 to 84 years old 2.1% | 1.7% male | 2.5% female (853 total)
- 85 years and over 3.3% | 1.6% male | 4.9% female (1310 total)

Wausau Household Type (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 39,906 total households
 - 2,938 male living alone
 - 5,618 male not living alone
 - 3,244 female living alone
 - 5,500 female not living alone

Wausau Households and Families (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 17,300 total family households
 - 2.24 average household size
 - 9,424 total families
 - 2.95 average family size
- 27.2% of households with one or more people under 18 years old
- 41.3% of households with one or more people 60 years and older

Wausau Demographics – Racial Makeup (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020)

- 31,298 White alone
- 672 Black or African American alone
- 292 Native American or Alaska Native alone
- 4,757 Asian alone

- 18 Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander alone
- 702 Some other race alone

Wausau Economic Status (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), (Pew Research Center, 2021)

- \$59,259 median income
- \$78,497 mean income
 - 4.6% less than \$10,000, lower class
 - 5.2% \$10,000 to \$14,999, lower class
 - 8.3% \$15,000 to \$24,999, lower class
 - 10.2% \$25,000 to \$34,999, lower class
 - 15% \$35,000 to \$49,999, lower to middle class
 - 17.7% \$50,000 to \$74,000, middle class
 - 14.5% \$75,000 to \$99,999, middle class
 - 14.9% 100,000 to 149,999, middle to upper class
 - 4.9% 150,000 to 199,999, upper class
 - 4.7% 200,000 or more, upper class

Wausau Education Levels (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- **Population 18-24:**
 - 11.1% less than a high school graduate
 - 42.4% High school graduate
 - 35.1% Some college or associate degree
 - 11.4% bachelor's degree or higher
- **Population 25 years or older:**

- 8.6% No high school diploma
- 29.4% High school graduate
- 20.1% Some college, no degree
- 10.9% associate degree
- 19.7% bachelor's degree
- 11.2% graduate or professional degree
- 91.4% total high school graduate or higher
- 31% total bachelor's degree or higher

Wausau Occupations (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 19,682 Civilian employed population 16 years and over:
 - Management, business, science, and arts occupations:
 - 6,995 total, 41.9% male | 49.2% female
 - Services occupations:
 - 3,957 total, 38.7% male | 61.3% female
 - Sales and office occupations:
 - 3,919 total, 41.4% male | 58.6% female
 - Natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations:
 - 1,163 total, 99.1% male | 0.9% female
 - Production, transportation, and material moving occupations:
 - 3,648 total, 75.8% male | 24.2% female

Stevens Point Wisconsin

Stevens Point in Wisconsin is a moderately sized community with a population of 25,666 people (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The age distribution shows a significantly higher young adult population, especially those between 20 and 24 years old, representing 20.7% of the population (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). This is likely because the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point being in this area. This age demographic skews slightly male. Children and adolescents, 15 to 19 years old, make up 12.3% (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). There is a notable decline in population percentages from the 30 to 34-year age group onwards, with the oldest age groups, 85 and over, comprising only 1.6% of the population, with more females than males in this senior bracket (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

The household composition is diverse, with 25,549 total households, of which 1,970 are males living alone, and 2,143 are females living alone (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The average household size is smaller at 2.10, while the average family size is larger at 2.90. There are 4,628 total families, and 28.9% of households have one or more people aged 60 years and older (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

Racially, Steven's Point is predominantly white, which includes 21,970 residents. There are smaller representations of Black or African American at 682 people, 1,232 people who are Asian, and other racial backgrounds (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020). This indicates a majority-white community with some racial diversity.

Economically, the city spans different income brackets, with a median income of \$53,611 and a mean income of \$70,485 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The majority of the population falls into the lower to middle-income categories (Pew Research Center, 2021), with 14.8% earning

between \$35,000 and \$49,999 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). A smaller proportion in the upper-income levels indicates a predominantly middle-class community.

Educationally, the population of Steven's Point is relatively well-educated, with 91.4% being high school graduates or higher among those 25 years and older (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). 31% hold a bachelor's degree or higher (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), suggesting a good level of higher education that correlates with the presence of young adults in the population.

Occupationally, the community has 5,352 people employed in management, business, science, and arts occupations, with more females at 56.3% than males at 43.7% in these fields (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). There are also considerable numbers in service and sales and office occupations, with a higher female presence in the latter. The traditional male-dominated fields such as natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations, and production, transportation, and material moving occupations are also represented, though to a lesser extent (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

Below are the demographical and geographical data points on the Stevens Point, Wisconsin public, for easier viewing.

Stevens Point City, Wisconsin Population Totals and Gender (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 15 to 19 years old total 12.3% | 12.4% male | 12.3% female (3152 total)
- 20 to 24 years old total 20.7% | 21.2% male | 20.1% female (5284 total)
- 25 to 29 years old total 7.3% | 7.4% male | 7.2% female (1866 total)
- 30 to 34 years old total 6.3% | 7.0% male | 5.7% female (1622 total)
- 35 to 39 years old total 7.0% | 7.0% male | 5.4% female (1592 total)
- 40 to 44 years old total 3.9% | 3.6% male | 4.3% female (1007 total)

- 45 to 49 years old total 5.6% | 5.9% male | 5.2% female (419 total)
- 50 to 54 years old total 4.4% | 4.1% male | 5.7% female (1125total)
- 55 to 59 years old total 3.8% | 4.0% male | 3.7% female (978 total)
- 60 to 64 years old total 4.5% | 4.9% male | 4.2% female (1162 total)
- 65 to 69 years old total 4.0% | 3.1% male | 4.9% female (1012 total)
- 70 to 74 years old total 2.9% | 2.9% male | 2.9% female (737 total)
- 75 to 79 years old total 2.9% | 2.5% male | 3.3% female (742 total)
- 80 to 84 years old 1.5% | 1.2% male | 1.7% female (374 total)
- 85 years and over 1.6% | 0.9% male | 2.4% female (415 total)

Steven's Point Household Type (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 25,549 total households
- 1,970 male living alone
- 3,118 male not living alone
- 2,143 female living alone
- 3,118 female not living alone

Steven's Point Households and Families (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 10,846 total households
- 2.10 average household size
- 4,628 total families
- 2.90 average family size
- 20.9% of households with one or more people under 18 years old
- 28.9% of households with one or more people 60 years and older

Steven's Point Demographics – Racial Makeup (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020)

- 21,970 white alone
- 682 Black or African American alone
- 158 Native American or Alaska Native alone
- 1,232 Asian alone
- 10 Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander alone
- 345 Some other race alone

Stevens Point Economic Status (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), (Pew Research Center, 2021)

- \$53,611 median income
- \$70,485 mean income
 - 4.9% less than \$10,000, lower class
 - 4.1% \$10,000 to \$14,999, lower class
 - 13.7% \$15,000 to \$24,999, lower class
 - 9.9% \$25,000 to \$34,999, lower class
 - 14.8% \$35,000 to \$49,999, lower to middle class
 - 17.3% \$50,000 to \$74,000, middle class
 - 14.5% \$75,000 to \$99,999, middle class
 - 12.2% \$100,000 to \$149,999, middle to upper class
 - 5.1% \$150,000 to \$199,999, upper class
 - 3.6% \$200,000 or more, upper class

Steven's Point Education Levels (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)**Population 18-24 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022):**

- 2.1% less than a high school graduate
- 24.7% High school graduate
- 62.4% Some college or associate degree
- 10.9% bachelor's degree or higher

Population 25 years or older (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022):

- 91.4% total high school graduate or higher
- 31% total bachelor's degree or higher
- 5.0% No high school diploma
- 27.6% High school graduate
- 18.7% Some college, no degree
- 11.1% associate degree
- 25.9% bachelor's degree
- 11.7% graduate or professional degree

Steven's Point Occupations (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 14,970 Civilian employed population 16 years and over
- Management, business, science, and arts occupations
 - 5,352 total, 43.7% male | 56.3% female
- Services occupations
 - 3,062 total, 46.6% male | 53.4% female
- Sales and office occupations
 - 2,958 total, 32.9% male | 67.1% female
- Natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations
 - 1,062 total, 95.7% male | 4.3% female

- Production, transportation, and material moving occupations
 - 2,563 total, 80.2% male | 19.8% female

Mosinee Wisconsin

Based on the U.S. Census Bureau data, Mosinee, Wisconsin, is a small city with a total population of 4,452 individuals (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The population exhibits a varied age distribution, with notable concentrations in the 20-24 and 25-29 age groups, particularly among females (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The gender distribution across different age groups varies, with a higher percentage of males and females in varied age groups.

There are 4,467 total households in Mosinee, with a larger number of males living alone compared to females living alone, but more females not living alone compared to their male counterparts (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The average household size is 2.09 people, while the average family size is larger at 2.71 people. Approximately one-fifth of households include someone under 18 years old, and slightly over 40% include someone 60 years or older, indicating a blend of young families and older residents (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

The racial composition of Mosinee is predominantly white, with very small representations of Black or African American, Native American or Alaska Native, and Asian residents (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020).

Economically, Mosinee displays a spectrum of income levels, with the largest percentages falling within the \$50,000 to \$74,999 and \$100,000 to \$149,999 brackets (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), which Pew Research Center classifies as middle and middle to upper income. The median income is \$68,219, and the mean income is \$76,778 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), which likely reflects a middle-class community.

In terms of education, the community is relatively well-educated, with 93.7% of those 25 and older having at least graduated high school and 25.8% having obtained a bachelor's degree or higher (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). 39.6% of adults aged 18-24 hold a bachelor's degree or higher (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

Occupationally, Mosinee's workforce has the largest number of people employed in management, business, science, and arts occupations (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). Notably, there is gender disparity in certain occupational fields; for example, natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations are exclusively male, and sales and office occupations are predominantly female (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022).

This data paints a picture of Mosinee as a small, predominantly white, and middle-class community with a balanced gender distribution, a decent level of education, and various occupations among its residents. Below are the demographical and geographical data points on the public of Mosinee, Wisconsin, for easier viewing.

Mosinee Population Totals and Gender (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 15 to 19 years old total 3.1% | 3.2% male | 3.1% female
- 20 to 24 years old total 14% | 4.3% male | 22.6% female
- 25 to 29 years old total 14.4% | 17.8% male | 11.4% female
- 30 to 34 years old total 5.7% | 5.1% male | 6.2% female
- 35 to 39 years old total 4.1% | 6.9% male | 1.6% female
- 40 to 44 years old total 4.8% | 3.6% male | 5.8% female
- 45 to 49 years old total 6.9% | 8.5% male | 5.5% female
- 50 to 54 years old total 4.9% | 6.4% male | 3.6% female
- 55 to 59 years old total 6.7% | 6.3% male | 7.1% female

- 60 to 64 years old total 4.1% | 5.7% male | 2.7% female
- 65 to 69 years old total 4.6% | 6.6% male | 2.8% female
- 70 to 74 years old total 4.5% | 3.3% male | 5.5% female
- 75 to 79 years old total 2.8% | 1.8% male | 3.7% female
- 80 to 84 years old 5.6% | 5.6% male | 5.6% female
- 85 years and over 1.4% | 0.8% male | 1.9% female

Mosinee Household Type (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 4,467 total households
- 346 male living alone
- 807 male not living alone
- 399 female living alone
- 579 female not living alone

Mosinee Households and Families (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 2,131 total households
- 2.09 average household size
- 1,005 total families
- 2.71 average family size
- 20.1% of households with one or more people under 18 years old (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)
- 40.2% of households with one or more people 60 years and older (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

Mosinee Demographics – Racial Makeup (U.S. Census Bureau, 2020)

- 4,143 white alone

- 16 Black or African American alone
- 15 Native American or Alaska Native alone
- 52 Asian alone
- 0 Native Hawaiian and Pacific Islander alone
- 37 Some other race alone

Mosinee Economic Status (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022), (Pew Research Center, 2021)

- \$68,219 median income
- \$76,778 mean income
 - 3.8% less than \$10,000, lower class
 - 3.3% \$10,000 to \$14,999, lower class
 - 3.9% \$15,000 to \$24,999, lower class
 - 11.9% \$25,000 to \$34,999, lower class
 - 13.1% \$35,000 to \$49,999, lower to middle class
 - 19.8% \$50,000 to \$74,000, middle class
 - 16.4% \$75,000 to \$99,999, middle class
 - 17.6% \$100,000 to \$149,999, middle to upper class
 - 8.5% \$150,000 to \$199,999, upper class
 - 1.6% \$200,000 or more, upper class

Mosinee Education Levels (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- **Population 18-24 (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022):**
 - 2.0% less than a high school graduate
 - 25.2% high school graduate

- 33.2% some college or associate degree
- 39.6% bachelor's degree or higher
- **Population 25 years or older (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022):**
- 6.3% no high school diploma
- 32% high school graduate
- 20.9% some college, no degree
- 15% associate degree
- 20.4% bachelor's degree
- 5.4% graduate or professional degree
- 93.7% total high school graduate or higher
- 25.8% total bachelor's degree or higher

Mosinee Occupations (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- 2,665 Civilian employed population 16 years and over
 - Management, business, science, and arts occupations
 - 1,236 total, 39% male | 61% female
 - Services occupations
 - 241 total, 46.1% male | 53.9% female
 - Sales and office occupations
 - 611 total, 33.7% male | 66.3% female
 - Natural resources, construction, and maintenance occupations
 - 167 total, 100% male | 0% female
 - Production, transportation, and material moving occupations
 - 404 total, 91.8% male | 8.2% female

Other Research

Workforce Status of Families in Mosinee

The statistics provided offer insight into the labor force participation within families in a specific demographic or area. Out of the total families surveyed:

- **Families with Only the Husband in the Labor Force and Wife Not:**
 - 23.4%, representing 178 families.
- **Families with Both Husband and Wife in the Labor Force:**
 - 56.0%, amounting to 426 families.
- **Families with Two or More Workers in the Past 12 Months:**
 - 52.9%, which totals 532 families.
- **Families with Only One Worker in the Past 12 Months:**
 - 34.6% of the population, or 348 families.

These figures indicate that more than half of the families have dual earners, which could reflect economic necessity or a cultural trend toward dual-income households. It's also noteworthy that the percentage of families with two or more workers exceeds the percentage of families where both husband and wife are in the labor force, suggesting that other family members may also be contributing to the workforce. The data underscores the diversity of family labor structures in the surveyed population.

Workforce Status in Stevens Point

- **Both Husband and Wife in the Labor Force:**
 - 62.4% (2041 total families)

- **Husband in Labor Force, Wife Not:**
 - 13.6% (444 families)
- **Employment Dynamics Over the Past 12 Months:**
 - One Worker: 28.4% (1313 total families)
 - Two or More Workers: 57.1% (2642 families)

Out of a total of 2041 families, a significant portion, 62.4%, consists of both the husband and wife participating in the labor force. Conversely, a smaller segment, representing 444 families (13.6%), indicates scenarios where only the husband is employed and the wife is not part of the labor force. When examining the employment dynamics within the past 12 months, the data further divides families based on the number of workers. Specifically, 1313 families, or 28.4% of the total, had one worker, whereas a larger proportion, 2642 families, which equate to 57.1%, reported having two or more workers. This distribution highlights the diverse employment situations among families, underscoring the varying degrees of labor force participation.

Workforce Status in Wausau

- **Total Families with Both Spouses in the Labor Force:**
 - 3765 families, making up 56.8%.
- **Families with Only the Husband in the Labor Force and Wife Not:**
 - 880 families, representing 13.3%.
- **Families Where a Spouse Worked Full-Time, Year-Round in the Past 12 Months:**
 - 2128 families, accounting for 31.7%.

In a detailed overview of family labor force participation, the data reveals diverse employment patterns among families. Specifically, out of the total families assessed, 56.8% (or 3765 families) have both the husband and wife actively participating in the labor force. A smaller segment, comprising 13.3% (or 880 families), shows instances where only the husband is employed while the wife remains out of the labor force. Additionally, a notable 31.7% (or 2128 families) of the total have at least one spouse who worked full-time, year-round over the past 12 months. This distribution showcases the various ways in which families engage with the labor market, highlighting the presence of both dual-earner households and those with a single income source.

Marital Status of Females

Mosinee

- Of females 35 to 44 years, 176 are married, 42.6%.
- Of females 45 to 54 years, 215 are married, 81.4%.

Wausau

- Of females, 35 to 44 years, 2641 are married, 52.4%
- Of females, 45 to 54 years, 2184 are married, 59.9%

Stevens Point

- Of females, 35 to 44 years, 1378 are married, 50.8%
- Of females, 45 to 54 years, 1297 are married, 51.2%

Language Spoken at Home

- Mosinee: Speak only English 4253 people 99.0%.

- Stevens Point: Speak only English 23293 people 94.7%
- Wausau: Speak only English 32939 people 87.8%

NEWS MEDIA PUBLICS

Local newspapers, typically published daily, are an important part of news media within a community. They provide in-depth coverage of local events, government actions, school activities, sports, and community issues. Print news media play a crucial role in keeping residents informed and can also offer editorial perspectives on local matters. They often provide a mix of print and digital offerings to cater to a broad audience.

Newspapers for Outreach in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Region

The Standard Rate and Data Service (SRDS) database was used to research key newspapers for outreach. The newspapers listed in the SRDS database are based on serving communities within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Designated Market Area (DMA) and cater to different cities within this region. They all share the common feature of being daily publications, which indicates they provide up-to-date news to their readers on a daily basis (*Standard Rate and Data Service, 2024*). Their circulation numbers provide insight into their reach within each community. The Whitewater PR Company chose newspapers in the areas where the key publics are located. Below, the targeted newspapers are described.

Wausau Daily Herald

- City: Wausau-Merrill, WI
- Circulation: Weekday: 2,841, Sunday: 5,942
- Evening (Mon-Fri), Sat and Sun Mornings.

The Wausau Daily Herald stands out for its higher circulation numbers, especially on Sundays. This suggests it has a significant presence in the Wausau-Merrill community, likely serving as a primary source of local news for its readers (*Standard Rate and Data Service*, 2024).

Times (Newspaper: Community)

- City: Mosinee, WI
- Circulation: Weekday: 1,800
- Published weekly–Thursday.

The Community Times, a newspaper serving Mosinee, WI, falls within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA. It has a weekday circulation of 1,800.

The Northwoods River News

- City: Rhineland, WI
- Published 3 days per week–Tuesday, Thursday, and Weekend (Saturday).

The Northwoods River News is a community newspaper located in Rhineland, WI, within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Stevens Point Journal

- City: Stevens Point, WI
- Circulation: Weekday: 1,821, Sunday: 5,594

The Stevens Point Journal's circulation numbers reveal its role in providing daily news to the Stevens Point area. It sees a significant rise in circulation on Sundays, indicating the importance of the Sunday edition to its readership (*Standard Rate and Data Service*, 2024).

Newspaper Analysis of Steven's Point, Mosinee, and Wausau Areas

The Wausau Daily Herald, with its higher circulation numbers peaking on Sundays, stands as a significant news source in the Wausau-Merrill community, indicating a strong readership bond and likely a primary source for local news, distinguished by its evening and weekend morning issues. In contrast, the Times of Mosinee, with a modest circulation of 1,800 and a weekly Thursday issue, appears to cater to its community with a more concentrated weekly news digest. Meanwhile, The Northwoods River News, while not specifying its circulation, suggests a thrice-weekly engagement with its readers in Rhinelander, providing a steady stream of local news. Lastly, the Stevens Point Journal mirrors a pattern seen in the Wausau Daily Herald, with its circulation jumping on Sundays, highlighting the community's preference for the comprehensive coverage typically found in Sunday editions, reinforcing the role of these local newspapers in their respective communities within the Wausau-Rhineland DMA.

Other Newspapers in Surrounding Areas

Antigo Times and Shopper

- City: Antigo, WI
- Circulation: Weekday: 12,718
- Newspaper: Community
- Published weekly–Monday

The Antigo Times and Shopper is a community newspaper serving the city of Antigo, WI, which is part of the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Antigo Daily Journal

- City: Antigo, WI

- Frequency: Evening (Mon-Fri) and Sat Morning ex. Sun.
- Newspaper: Daily

The Antigo Daily Journal is a daily newspaper located in Antigo, WI, and operates within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Daily Tribune

- City: Wisconsin Rapids, WI
- Frequency: Evening (Mon-Fri), Sat and Sun Mornings.
- Newspaper: Daily
- Circulation: Weekday: 2,022 Sunday: 5,750

The Daily Tribune, a daily newspaper based in Wisconsin Rapids, WI, falls within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA. It reports a circulation of 2,022 on weekdays and significantly increases to 5,750 on Sundays.

Lakeland Times

- City: Minocqua, WI
- Newspaper: Community
- Frequency: Published every week—Tuesday and Friday.

The Lakeland Times is a community newspaper serving Minocqua, WI, which is part of the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Leader

- City: Tomahawk, WI
- Newspaper: Community
- Frequency: Published weekly—Wednesday.

The Leader is a community newspaper located in Tomahawk, WI, within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Marshfield News-Herald

- City: Marshfield, WI
- Circulation: Weekday: 1,918 Sunday: 5,686
- Newspaper: Daily
- Frequency: Evening (Mon-Fri), Sat and Sun Mornings.

The Marshfield News-Herald, a daily newspaper situated in Marshfield, WI, operates within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA. It has a weekday circulation of 1,918 and a Sunday circulation of 5,686.

North Woods Trader

- City: Eagle River, WI
- Frequency: Published weekly–Wednesday.
- Newspaper: Community

The North Woods Trader is a community newspaper based in Eagle River, WI, part of the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Price County Review

- City: Park Falls, WI
- Newspaper: Community
- Frequency: Published weekly–Thursday

The Price County Review is a community newspaper serving Park Falls, WI, which is within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Three Lakes News

- Newspaper: Community
- City: Eagle River, WI
- Frequency: Published weekly–Wednesday.

The Three Lakes News is a community newspaper located in Eagle River, WI, operating within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Vilas County News-Review

- City: Eagle River, WI
- Frequency: Published weekly–Wednesday.
- Newspaper: Community

The Vilas County News-Review is a community newspaper based in Eagle River, WI, within the Wausau-Rhineland, WI DMA.

Analysis of Other Newspapers in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Area

The Wausau-Rhineland DMA is served by a network of newspapers catering to diverse preferences. The Antigo Times and Shopper leads with high circulation for its weekly release, indicative of its strong community presence. It contrasts with the Antigo Daily Journal's daily distribution, offering consistent news to the same community. The Daily Tribune shows a substantial jump in Sunday circulation, echoing the demand for weekend content in Wisconsin Rapids. Community newspapers like Minocqua's Lakeland Times, Tomahawk's Leader, and Eagle River's North Woods Trader maintain weekly touchpoints with their readers, providing localized content. The Marshfield News-Herald maintains a daily readership with a peak on Sundays, matching the trend for in-depth weekend editions. The Price County Review, Three Lakes News, and Vilas County News-Review are vital in their respective locales, highlighting

the role of community-centric news. This mix of daily and weekly, small, and large circulation figures showcases a dynamic local media landscape across central and northern Wisconsin.

Radio Stations in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Region

Local radio stations provide another essential medium for news and information, with formats ranging from talk radio to news bulletins that interact with music programming. They provide immediate news updates, traffic reports, weather alerts, and community announcements. Radio stations can be particularly important in areas where people spend significant time commuting and rely on timely audio updates.

The Wausau-Stevens Point area, part of the Wausau-Rhineland DMA, hosts a variety of radio stations catering to listeners interested in talk and news information (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024). Below is an overview of the stations that offer local news on their channels.

- **WFHR-AM 1320:** This station focuses on a progressive talk format, targeting an audience primarily aged 35 and above. Its programming likely includes discussions on contemporary issues, politics, and social matters from a progressive perspective. They also include some local news updates (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024).
- **WLBL-AM 930:** Operating with a public radio and news format, WLBL-AM serves the community with a mix of news coverage, cultural programming, and educational content. This station is part of Wisconsin's public radio network, offering a broad spectrum of topics relevant to its listeners (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024).
- **WSAU-AM 550:** This station operates under the talk radio and news/talk formats, catering to an audience aged 35 to 64 years old. They likely provide a mix of local, national, and international news coverage, talk shows, and discussions on various topics of interest to their demographic (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024).

- **WSAU-FM 99.9:** This station operates under the talk radio and news/talk formats, catering to an audience aged 35 to 64 years old. They likely provide a mix of local, national, and international news coverage, talk shows, and discussions on various topics of interest to their demographic (*Standard Rate & Data Service, 2024*).
- **WXCO-AM 1230:** This station also embraces a progressive talk format for listeners aged 35 to 64. Similar to WFHR-AM, WXCO-AM features content that includes liberal perspectives on political, social, and cultural issues. This radio station also includes local news coverage (*Standard Rate & Data Service, 2024*).
- **Wisconsin Public Radio Affiliate:** Wisconsin Public Radio (WPR) is a public radio network dedicated to serving the people of Wisconsin with quality news, cultural content, and music programming. It operates under the auspices of the Wisconsin Educational Communications Board and the University of Wisconsin-Madison, partnering with local, national, and international news organizations to offer a wide array of programs. With a strong online presence through wpr.org, WPR connects communities across the state with the latest news, ongoing cultural events, and educational opportunities. As a member of the National Public Radio (NPR) network, it also provides access to national and global news, supporting a well-informed public.

While other stations in the area, such as WOSQ-FM 92.3 and WRIG-AM 1390, focus on sports content targeting men aged 25 to 54, the stations listed above specifically cater to audiences seeking talk and news programming. Central Wisconsin's radio landscape offers listeners a variety of content, spanning educational material on public radio to the diverse opinions found on progressive talk and news stations. Below are stations that focus on sports and other broadcasting.

Other Radio Stations in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Area

- **WOSQ-FM 92.3:** WOSQ-FM 92.3 is a sports format radio station broadcasting to the Central Wisconsin area, specifically within the Wausau-Stevens Point MSA and Wausau-Rhineland DMA. The station primarily targets men aged 25-54, catering to a demographic that is traditionally enthusiastic about sports content, from live games to sports talk and analysis.
- **WRIG-AM 1390:** WRIG-AM 1390 is a sports-focused radio station operating within the Wausau-Stevens Point Metropolitan Statistical Area and the Wausau-Rhineland Designated Market Area in Central Wisconsin. It targets the 25-54 male demographic, providing them with sports programming that resonates with their interests.

Key TV Stations for Outreach in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI Region

Local television stations broadcast news segments that cover a wide range of local interest stories, from breaking news and weather forecasts to human interest pieces and investigative reporting. They usually have several news broadcasts throughout the day, including morning, midday, and evening slots, to reach a wide audience (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024). These stations often affiliate with national networks but maintain a strong focus on the local news that affects their immediate viewing area.

The Wausau-Rhineland, WI area is served by various local TV stations catering to diverse interests and affiliations. Below is a brief overview of each station that features local news.

WAOW-TV (Channel 9)

WAOW-TV is a commercial TV station affiliated with ABC (American Broadcasting Company) (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024). It serves the Wausau-Rhineland DMA and

offers a mix of news, entertainment, and sports programming typical of ABC's national lineup, along with local news and community programming (*News 9 WAOW*, n.d.). WAOW-TV broadcasts its local news on weekdays at 6:00 a.m., 12:00 p.m., 5:00 p.m., 6:00 p.m., and 10:00 p.m. On weekends, the local news is at 6:00 p.m. and 10:00 p.m. (*News 9 WAOW*, 2024). There is also a morning broadcast titled "Wake Up Wisconsin Weekend" at 6:00 a.m. on weekends, which may include local news segments (*News 9 WAOW*, 2024).

WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16)

WJFW-TV is a commercial station affiliated with NBC (National Broadcasting Company) (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024). It broadcasts a range of NBC programming, including popular series, daytime shows, late-night talk shows, and extensive news coverage (*WJFW-TV*, n.d.). Local news and regional programming also feature prominently in its schedule. WJFW-TV broadcasts their local news in the Wausau area at 10:00 p.m. on Saturdays under the program title "Newswatch 12 at 10 p.m. Saturday" and also has a segment called "Newswatch 12 Weekend," which is the local news broadcast on Sundays, also at 10:00 p.m. Additionally, there is a program called "Newswatch 12 Weekend," which is the local news broadcast on Sundays at 10:00 p.m. (*WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16)*, 2024).

WSAW-TV (Channel 7)

WSAW-TV is a commercial station affiliated with CBS (Columbia Broadcasting System) (*Standard Rate & Data Service*, 2024). It offers a comprehensive lineup of CBS network programming, including prime-time television shows, daytime dramas, news magazines, and sports (*WSAW / Wausau, NorthCentral Wisconsin / News, Sports, Weather*, n.d.). Local news and regional content are also key components of its offerings. WSAW-TV broadcasts their local news, NewsChannel 7, at 6:00 p.m. and again at 10:00 p.m. (*Programming Schedule*, 2024).

These times apply to their weekday schedule. On weekends, WSAW-TV broadcasts their local news, NewsChannel 7, at 6:00 p.m. on Saturday and Sunday. Additionally, the local news is aired at 10:00 p.m. on both days (*Programming Schedule, 2024*).

Network Affiliates

Each TV station mentioned in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI area is affiliated with a national network, making them network affiliates (*Standard Rate & Data Service, 2024*). Here is a summary of their affiliations:

- **WAOW-TV (Channel 9):** Affiliated with ABC (American Broadcasting Company).
- **WJFW-TV (Channel 12, DT Channel 16):** Affiliated with NBC (National Broadcasting Company).
- **WSAW-TV (Channel 7):** Affiliated with CBS (Columbia Broadcasting System).

Being network affiliates means these stations broadcast content provided by their respective networks, including national news, sports, entertainment programs, and special events, alongside local news and other regional programming tailored to the interests and needs of viewers in the Wausau-Rhineland area ("*Network affiliate,*" 2024).

Independents

All TV stations in the Wausau-Rhineland, WI area are affiliated with national networks, and none are listed as independent in the SRDS database. Independent stations are those that are not affiliated with any national network (such as ABC, CBS, NBC, PBS, FOX, or ION) and typically offer a diverse range of content, including locally produced programs, syndicated shows not picked up by network affiliates, movies, and specialty programming (*INDEPENDENT STATION Collocation / Meaning and Examples of Use, 2024*). Each station

above is tied to a specific national network, providing content in alignment with that network's programming alongside their local news and regional content.

Now that the geographic and demographic publics and the print, radio, and broadcast publics have been described, the two target publics for the Walk of Feats fundraiser are explained below, using the data gathered from the research.

Research on Traditional News Media

When asked which of these platforms they prefer to get news on, nearly six in ten Americans say they prefer a digital device (58%), more than they prefer TV (27%). Even fewer Americans prefer radio (6%) or print (5%) (PEW Research Center, 2024).

News consumption across platforms

% of U.S. adults who ___ get news from ...

Note: Figures may not add up to 100% due to rounding.
 Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

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Among digital platforms, news websites or apps are also the most preferred source for news: A quarter of U.S. adults prefer to get their news this way, compared with 15% who prefer search, 12% who prefer social media, and 6% who say they prefer podcasts (PEW Research Center, 2023).

News consumption across digital platforms

% of U.S. adults who ___ get news from ...

Note: Figures may not add up to 100% due to rounding. Respondents who do not have internet access at home did not receive these questions; they are included with those who said "Never," along with those who say they do not get news from digital devices. Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

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Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

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Research on Social Media

Most U.S. adults use YouTube and Facebook; about half use Instagram

% of U.S. adults who say they *ever* use ...

Note: Respondents who did not give an answer are not shown.
Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted May 19-Sept. 5, 2023.
"Americans' Social Media Use"

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

YouTube is the most popular among people, with 83% of U.S. adults saying they ever use it. Facebook follows at 68%. About half of the adults, or 47%, report using Instagram, while Pinterest and TikTok are used by 35% and 33%, respectively (PEW Research Center, 2023). LinkedIn is utilized by 30% of adults, slightly edging out WhatsApp and Snapchat, which are used by 29% and 27% of the population, respectively (PEW Research Center, 2023). Twitter and Reddit are both used by 22% of adults. The least used platform among those listed is BeReal, with only 3% of U.S. adults reporting they ever use it (PEW Research Center, 2023).

TWO TARGET PUBLICS FOR THE WALK OF FEATS FUNDRAISER

For the Walk of Feats fundraiser organized by Teal 2 Heal, a nonprofit organization, identifying the right public is vital for the success of the PR campaign by Whitewater PR

Digital news platform preferences

% of U.S. adults who *prefer* ____ for getting news

Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

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Company. Our task as public relations professionals are to find two key publics, through which our research points us in the direction of to target for this specific public relations campaign.

In addition to key publics, potential allies for the Walk of Feats fundraiser PR Campaign and Teal 2 Heal nonprofit organization include Aspirus Wausau Hospital, including their Aspirus Cancer Care - Rhinelander - James Beck Cancer Center, Marshfield Medical Center-Weston, and Aspirus Stevens Point Hospital, which are all within the area.

Based on the detailed research conducted on the Teal 2 Heal nonprofit organization and the communities within central Wisconsin, the two key publics we are targeting for the Walk of Feats fundraising campaign are as follows.

Women in Mosinee, Wausau, and Stevens Point Aged 45 to 69

Targeting women aged 45 to 69 in these regions could be particularly effective due to their inherent vulnerability to ovarian cancer (*Ovarian Cancer Risk Factors / Risk Factors for Ovarian Cancer*, 2024). Given their biological susceptibility, this risk makes the cause more salient to them. As suggested by previous research, certain people give because of sympathy and empathy (Small, Loewenstein & Slovic, 2007; Cryder & Loewenstein, 2008, loc. cit. Aaker & Akutsu, 2009). Women tend to feel sympathetic and empathetic toward other women who have ovarian cancer.

Another reason this public would be a good target is that whether one gives and how much one gives may be activated by the context in which one is asked (Wheeler, DeMarree & Petty, 2007, loc. cit. Aaker & Akutsu, 2009). For example, if the request involves a donation or volunteering at a cancer-related event, such as the Walk of Feats fundraiser, the chance of an individual accepting and going with will increase significantly when one's family identity is salient (Wheeler, DeMarree & Petty 2007 loc. cit. Aaker & Akutsu, 2009). In other words, when

the request is made by a family member, like by the mother, the other family members are more likely to abide and join along.

Targeting mothers in family-oriented communities for charitable events like the Walk of Feats fundraiser is strategic due to their inherent empathy and potential personal connection to ovarian cancer because of their biological susceptibility (*Ovarian Cancer Risk Factors / Risk Factors for Ovarian Cancer*, 2024). This shared experience may make the cause more salient and inspire generosity (Small, Loewenstein & Slovic, 2007; Cryder & Loewenstein, 2008, loc. cit. Aaker & Akutsu, 2009). Aligning this with an event structured to be inclusive for all ages ensures that these mothers, alongside their families, including their very young children, their pre-teen children, their adult children, husbands, and more, can participate meaningfully. By integrating the event's family-friendly challenges with the shared experiences of the targeted public, the event can spread quickly by word-of-mouth or social media because of the large diversity that families include.

Simple cross-tabulation analysis indicates that personal asks from people they know well are a significant factor in the decision to donate (Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005). In this case, for our public, it would be the mother in the family. Also, Wolff (1999, loc. cit. Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005) notes that women tend to be more altruistic than men. In addition, Jencks (1987 loc. cit. Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005) and Andreoni, Brown, and Rischall (2003 loc. cit. Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005) find that marriage positively relates to giving. The Census Bureau shows 9,424 total families in Wausau, 4,628 total families in Stevens Point, and 1,005 total families in Mosinee (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). That is a total of 15,057 families, which shows that our public is large enough for targeting.

In addition to their families being involved in the fundraiser, medically, ovarian cancer is rare in women younger than 40. Most ovarian cancers develop after menopause. (*Ovarian Cancer Risk Factors / Risk Factors for Ovarian Cancer*, 2024). Most women experience menopause between the ages of 45 and 55 as a natural part of biological aging (World Health Organization: WHO, 2022). There are a total of 5,864 women aged between 45 and 69 in the Wausau area, there are a total of 2,848 women aged between 45 and 69 in the Stevens Point area, and there are a total of 513 women aged between 45 and 69 in the Mosinee area (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). This is a total of 9,225 women. These numbers indicate enough of this public to target our public relations campaign. The second key public is described in detail below.

Explanation and Demographics

In Wausau, women aged 45 to 69 are involved in professional fields such as management, business, science, and arts, indicating a high level of education and professional achievement that supports a stable middle-class lifestyle (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). A majority are white.

Age by Sex Female (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022)

- Wausau: 45 to 49 years 974, 50 to 54 years 1,009
- Stevens Point: 45 to 49 years 656, 50 to 54 years 591
- Mosinee: 45 to 49 years 130, 50 to 54 years 85

In Stevens Point, the influence of the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point may be reflected in these women's roles in academic and professional sectors. Despite a slightly lower economic status compared to Wausau, women in this age group contribute significantly to the middle-class community, with many engaged in education and service-oriented professions (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). Their high educational attainment shows active participation in the

workforce and community life. Mosinee's women's high educational levels and participation in management and professional occupations suggest they are vital economic contributors. The comfortable middle-class incomes of this demographic support their engagement in various community roles and activities. Overall, women aged 45 to 69 in these communities embody a mix of experience and professional success. They are well-educated and economically active.

In Mosinee, 25.3% of women aged 45 to 64 hold a bachelor's degree or higher (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). In Stevens Point, this figure is 29.5%, and in Wausau, it's slightly higher at 32.0% (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). These statistics underscore that a significant portion of women in these cities have pursued higher education, potentially leading to increased career opportunities and socio-economic mobility (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). This demographic's attainment of advanced degrees positions them for leadership roles and substantial contributions to community development across various sectors. 52% to 60% of these women are in the workforce along with their husbands or alone.

Traditional News Media Usage Among This Public

Women in the 50-64 age group sometimes watch television (72%) to get their news (PEW Research Center, 2023). Women, overall, at least sometimes get their news from television slightly more than men (65% vs. 61%) and use digital devices at the same rate (86%) (PEW Research Center, 2023). Middle-income individuals also at least sometimes get their news from television over radio and print as their source of traditional news.

Women in general (30%) prefer to get their news from television sources over radio and print for traditional media. 36% of individuals prefer getting their news from television over radio and print for traditional media (PEW Research Center, 2023).

Who uses each news platform

News consumption across platforms varies by age, gender, race, ethnicity, educational attainment and political leaning. Americans ages 50 and older are more likely than younger adults to turn to and prefer television and print publications.

News platform use | Digital platform use
 % of U.S. adults in each demographic group who get news at least sometimes from ...

	Television	Radio	Print publications	Digital devices
Total	62%	52%	37%	86%
Men	61%	51%	35%	86%
Women	65%	53%	38%	86%
Ages 18-29	41%	37%	24%	89%
30-49	53%	52%	29%	90%
50-64	72%	62%	39%	86%
65+	85%	52%	55%	77%
White	62%	54%	38%	86%
Black	76%	54%	39%	80%
Hispanic	62%	48%	32%	87%
Asian*	52%	42%	32%	93%
High school or less	67%	53%	37%	77%
Some college	63%	51%	35%	89%
College+	57%	51%	37%	93%
Lower income	61%	48%	34%	80%
Middle income	64%	53%	37%	88%
Upper income	60%	52%	38%	92%
Rep/Lean Rep	63%	54%	35%	85%
Dem/Lean Dem	63%	50%	38%	87%

*Estimates for Asian adults are representative of English speakers only.
 Note: White, Black and Asian adults include those who report being only one race and are not Hispanic; Hispanic adults are of any race.
 Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

News platform preference | Digital platform preference
 % of U.S. adults in each demographic group who say they prefer ____ for getting news

	Television	Radio	Print publications	Digital devices
Total	27%	6%	5%	58%
Men	25%	7%	5%	61%
Women	30%	6%	5%	55%
Ages 18-29	8%	3%	4%	83%
30-49	17%	8%	3%	69%
50-64	36%	8%	4%	48%
65+	50%	5%	10%	30%
White	28%	8%	6%	55%
Black	38%	4%	4%	50%
Hispanic	23%	4%	4%	65%
Asian*	16%	4%	2%	78%
High school or less	37%	5%	5%	48%
Some college	25%	6%	4%	62%
College+	19%	8%	6%	65%
Lower income	30%	5%	4%	57%
Middle income	29%	7%	5%	57%
Upper income	19%	9%	6%	64%
Rep/Lean Rep	27%	8%	5%	57%
Dem/Lean Dem	28%	6%	5%	59%

*Estimates for Asian adults are representative of English speakers only.
 Note: White, Black and Asian adults include those who report being only one race and are not Hispanic; Hispanic adults are of any race.
 Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted Sept. 25-Oct. 1, 2023.

Social Media Usage Among This Public

How use of online platforms – such as Facebook, Instagram or TikTok – differs among some U.S. demographic groups

% of U.S. adults who say they **ever** use ...

* Estimates for Asian adults are representative of English speakers only.

Note: White, Black and Asian adults include those who report being only one race and are not Hispanic. Hispanic adults are of any race. Not all numerical differences between groups shown are statistically significant. Respondents who did not give an answer are not shown.

Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted May 19-Sept. 5, 2023.

"Americans' Social Media Use"

PEW RESEARCH CENTER

In the United States, Facebook is used by 76% of women, a figure that surpasses usage rates of other social media platforms such as Instagram at 54%, Pinterest at 50%, and TikTok at 40%, and it is significantly higher compared to various other platforms (PEW Research Center, 2023). When looking at demographic distributions, 69% of the white population engages with Facebook. Among adults aged 30 to 49, Facebook's usage rate stands at 75%, which not only exceeds Instagram's 59% but also dwarfs the usage rates of other social media platforms (PEW Research Center, 2023). For the age group of 50 to 64, Facebook's prevalence is notably high, eclipsing that of Instagram, Pinterest, and other platforms. Additionally, Pinterest shows a

gendered preference in its user base; 50% of women use Pinterest, compared to only 19% of men, highlighting a significant disparity in platform usage based on gender (PEW Research Center, 2023).

Students in Stevens Point at UW-Stevens Point and Technical Schools Aged 20-24

According to the U.S. Census Bureau, there is a significant increase in the young adult population in Stevens Point, especially those between 20 and 24 years old, representing 20.7% of the population or 5,284 total people (U.S. Census Bureau, 2022). The increase in the young adult population is because of the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point, where college students attend. According to the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point website, they have an active enrollment of over 8,000 students (*University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point*, n.d.). This indicates enough of this public to target for a successful public relations campaign.

This demographic of college students is often looking for ways to engage in community service, social activities, and causes they care about. For example, college students have long been involved in efforts to develop more just and equitable societies (Keniston, 1973; McAdam, 1986, 1988, loc. cit. Broido, 2000). This involvement has been evidenced in students' participation in community service activities and efforts to ensure greater racial diversity in the student body and the faculty (Dalton, 1991, loc. cit. Broido, 2000). In other words, the higher one's social justice-related self-efficacy and the more positive one's outcome expectations specific to social justice activities, the more likely one will become interested in social justice-specific activities (Miller et al., 2009). This indicates that students at the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point are inclined to give back to a social justice issue, including the awareness of ovarian cancer.

The Walk of Feats fundraiser offers a unique blend of competition, social interaction, and philanthropy, making it attractive to Gen-Z, who value experiences and social impact. Wolpert (1995, loc. cit. Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005) finds that giving rates are higher where the political and cultural ideology is liberal rather than conservative. In addition, Surveys (e.g., ISGV, AAFRC, and Gallup) consistently find that increases in educational attainment are directly correlated with increased giving (Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005). This is consistent with the work done by other scholars (Feldstein & Clotfelter, 1976; Jencks, 1987; Morgan, Dye, & Hybels, 1977, loc. cit. Van Slyke & Brooks, 2005). This means that college students are more inclined to give their time to charitable events.

Stevens Point's substantial young adult and Gen-Z residents, connected to local educational institutions, are a vital audience for the Teal 2 Heal Walk of Feats fundraiser. Their liberal ideology and educational attainment, aligned with increased charitable giving, make them ideal participants for an event combining social interaction with philanthropy. The Walk of Feats fundraiser's interactive format and community-driven approach are especially appealing, promising active participation and the potential for long-term support for ovarian cancer initiatives.

Mid-State Technical College, Stevens Point Campus

Mid-State Technical College, Stevens Point Campus, is a part of the larger Mid-State Technical College (MSTC) system located in central Wisconsin, United States. MSTC is a comprehensive technical college providing education and training in various fields to meet the needs of both students and local employers.

The Stevens Point Campus specifically offers a range of programs and courses designed to prepare students for careers in diverse industries such as healthcare, business, manufacturing,

information technology, and more. It serves as a hub for education and skill development in the Stevens Point area and surrounding communities.

The Stevens Point Campus offers a variety of programs and courses including associate degrees, technical diplomas, and certificate programs that are tailored to meet the demands of the local job market. These programs emphasize hands-on training and practical skills necessary for entry-level positions in specific industries. The campus features modern facilities equipped with labs, workshops, computer labs, and other resources essential for technical education and training. These facilities are designed to simulate real-world work environments and enhance the learning experience.

The campus is staffed with experienced faculty and staff dedicated to student success, often bringing industry expertise and providing personalized support throughout students' academic journeys. Additionally, the campus engages with the community by collaborating with local businesses, industries, and organizations to align programs with current workforce needs. This collaboration may include internship opportunities, partnerships for job placement, and advisory committees composed of industry professionals. Furthermore, the Stevens Point Campus may offer continuing education courses, professional development workshops, and customized training programs for individuals seeking to upgrade their skills or advance in their careers, emphasizing its commitment to lifelong learning and workforce development.

Explanation and Demographics

The data from the U.S. Census Bureau suggests that in Stevens Point, the majority of individuals aged 18-24 have pursued education beyond high school, with 62.4% having some college experience or having attained an associate degree. This high percentage indicates that a significant portion of this age group is likely to be currently enrolled in college or has completed

some form of higher education, reflecting the value placed on post-secondary education in the area and potentially pointing to a relatively educated young adult population in Stevens Point.

Stevens Point, Wisconsin, with a population of 25,666, has a notable concentration of young adults aged 20 to 24, constituting 20.7% of its total population. This demographic trend is largely driven by the presence of the University of Wisconsin-Stevens Point in the area, attracting a significant portion of individuals in this age group.

Educationally, the community showcases a well-educated population, with 62.4% of individuals aged 20 to 24 having some college experience or an associate degree, indicating a strong emphasis on higher education within this age group.

In summary, Stevens Point presents itself as a community with a significant population of young adults aged 20 to 24, actively engaged in higher education pursuits and contributing to the city's social and economic landscape.

Those with some college education and those with a college degree report using Instagram at somewhat higher rates than those who have a high school degree or less education (Pew Research Center, 2024).

Social Media Usage Among This Public

To spread awareness for the Walk of Feats fundraising event and Teal 2 Heal nonprofit organization, the team currently uses word-of-mouth marketing, poster, and flier print media. This is because they have connections with graphic designers and printers, so there are many posters and street signs to get the word out about the event (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024). In addition to that, they have a Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn account that is not super actively used (L. Olszewski personal communication, retrieved via video, Feb 21, 2024).

In addition to targeting the traditional key news media publics that are listed above and using the print methods, we recommend the use of social media platforms and a social media campaign.

Although the currently most used media for awareness of the Walk of Feats fundraiser are word-of-mouth and print media, using digital and social media is a strategy to think about. This is because Gen-Z residents, who are college students in Stevens Point, have high educational ties, digital savviness, and increased social activism (Keniston, 1973; McAdam, 1986, 1988, loc. cit. Broido, 2000). According to Pew Research Center, a large percentage of college-aged adults use social media. Respectively, 78% use Instagram, 67% use Facebook, and 65% use Snapchat (*Demographics of Social Media Users and Adoption in the United States*, 2024). The post-event socializing will also help with shared media, promising effective promotion via social media for ovarian cancer support. Engaging this group through digital channels they frequently use will enhance the likelihood of a successful event.

Conclusion

By tailoring the campaign's messaging and outreach strategies to these two publics, Whitewater PR Company can increase awareness of the Walk of Feats Fundraiser, therefore enhancing participation in the event and, in turn, supporting Teal 2 Heal's mission to bring awareness to ovarian cancer.

Who uses each social media platform?

Usage of the major online platforms varies by factors such as age, gender and level of formal education.

% of U.S. adults who say they ever use __ by ...

AGE	GENDER	RACE & ETHNICITY	INCOME	EDUCATION	COMMUNITY	POLITICAL AFFILIATION
Facebook						
Instagram						
LinkedIn						
Twitter (X)						
Pinterest						
Snapchat						
YouTube						
WhatsApp						
Reddit						
TikTok						
BeReal						

Note: Respondents who did not give an answer are not shown.

Source: Survey of U.S. adults conducted May 19-Sept. 5, 2023.

Fig. 1 Who Uses Each Social Media Platform

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